

GEOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS WITH RESPECT TO GOLD MINERALIZATION OF BENI/KAFIN-KORO AREA (PART OF SHEET 165, BISHINI SW), NORTH-CENTRAL, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

A total of 21 samples were analyzed in the laboratory, Inductively Coupled Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectrum (ICP-AES) was employed in the whole rock analysis for oxides, total sulphide (TOS), total carbon (TOC) and loss on ignition (LOI), while Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectroscopy (ICP-MS) was employed in the analysis for trace metals including gold, and rare earth elements (REE) that were either associated with or served as pathfinder for gold. Statistical analyses revealed an anomaly of about 5.3ppm Au around Beni (within the schist), while the threshold of 2.6ppm runs from the northwest axis to the eastern part of the area (within the granite and gneiss). On the whole, a background value ranging between (0.5 – 0.8) ppm Au was also established.

KEYWORDS: Gold Mineralization, Beni/Kafin-Koro, Trace Elements, Rare Earth Elements (REE)

GEOLOGY

Generally, the area of study falls within the North-Central Basement Complex of Nigeria, characterised by the Migmatite Gneiss Complex, Older Granite and the Schists. The basement rocks are of three lithological units (Ajibade *et al.*, 1988). Locally, the area of study falls within the syn-tectonic older granite rocks, characterized by the coarse-grained and the medium-grained sizes. The coarser grain sizes occupy the southern portion of the area while the medium-to fine grain size dominates the northern part of the study area (Figure 1). There are series of intrusions and tectonics (folding and shearing) that probably led to the mineralization.

Figure 1. Geological map of the study area; showing the lithological units.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

A total of 21 samples were analyzed. Spectroscopy is one of the broad methods of analyzing minerals. It involves the interaction of light and matter and has both physical and analytical applications (Hoffman et al, 1996). For this research, the Inductive Coupled Plasma – Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES) and Inductive Coupled Plasma – Mass Spectroscopy (ICP-MS) methods were employed. Unlike most other geochemical analysis methods, inductively coupled plasma spectrometry (ICP) is generally superior in accuracy, precision, detection limit, freedom from interferences, and dynamic range than other analytical instrumentations. One can analyze a solution for many elements in 1 minute using (ICP-AES), as a result, large volumes of data can be generated very fast (Boumans, 2000; Vela et al, 1993). The inductively coupled plasma – mass spectroscopy (ICP-MS) was employed to determine the trace and rare earth (REE) metals and establish spatial degree of variation of those that are associated with gold mineralization, and to decipher the likely source of gold mineralization within the area of study. While, inductively coupled plasma – atomic emission spectrum (ICP-AES) was employed for the whole rock analysis where relative percentages of all the oxides present in the rock samples and loss on ignition (LOI) were determined.

RESULTS

The results are presented in Figures 1 - 4 and Tables 1 - 8.

Table 1: Concentrations of Some Selected Trace Elements in Coarse-Grained Granites

S/N	Trace Element	Au	As	Ag	Cu	Zn	Mo	Ni
	Sample	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
1.	L21	0.50	0.50	0.10	2.40	23.00	0.30	3.50
2.	L28	0.50	0.50	0.10	8.60	54.00	0.30	11.30
3.	L29	0.60	0.50	0.10	2.90	30.00	0.20	3.80
4.	L30	0.50	0.50	0.10	3.50	35.00	0.40	8.30
5.	L37	0.50	0.50	0.10	16.00	71.00	0.20	10.30
	Average:	0.52	0.50	0.10	5.80	42.60	0.28	7.44

Table 2: Concentrations of Some Selected Trace Elements in Fine-Grained Granites

S/N	Trace Element	Au	As	Ag	Cu	Zn	Mo	Ni
	Sample	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
1.	L3	0.50	0.50	0.10	7.00	78.00	0.30	29.10
2.	L6	0.50	0.50	0.10	9.20	41.00	0.20	13.30
3.	L7	0.50	0.60	0.10	38.60	68.00	0.20	33.80
4.	L9	0.50	0.50	0.10	21.50	82.00	0.20	20.70
5.	L10	0.50	0.70	0.10	54.70	78.00	0.20	30.20
6.	L13	0.50	0.60	0.10	3.10	42.00	0.20	25.30
7.	L14	0.50	0.50	0.10	3.50	37.00	0.20	18.10
	Average:	0.50	0.56	0.10	19.66	60.86	0.21	24.36

Table 3: Concentrations of Some Selected Trace Elements in Migmatite-Gneiss

S/N	Trace Element	Au	As	Ag	Cu	Zn	Mo	Ni
	Sample	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
1.	L18	0.80	0.50	0.10	1.90	22.00	0.30	4.20
2.	L25	0.60	0.50	0.10	2.50	22.00	0.30	2.50
3.	L26	0.50	0.50	0.10	2.60	27.00	0.30	3.00
4.	L27	0.50	0.50	0.10	17.50	124.00	0.30	46.60
5.	L39	0.80	0.60	0.10	41.90	75.00	0.20	23.80
	Average:	0.64	0.52	0.10	13.28	54.00	0.28	23.58

Table 4: Concentrations of Some Selected Trace Elements in Schist

S/N	Trace Element	Au	As	Ag	Cu	Zn	Mo	Ni
	Sample	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm
1.	L15	5.30	1.10	0.10	4.90	43.00	0.30	13.80
2.	L16	0.70	0.50	0.10	19.20	135.00	0.40	6.90
3.	L17	0.50	0.50	0.10	4.00	81.00	0.30	6.40
4.	L38	2.60	1.10	0.10	6.80	41.00	0.40	16.50
	Average:	2.28	0.80	0.10	8.72	75.00	0.35	10.90

Table 5: Concentrations of Some Selected Rare Earth Elements (REEs) in Coarse-Grained Porphyritic Granite

Elements	Th	Co	Rb	Ba	Zr	Hf	Nb	Ta	Ti	Ni	K	Ca	Sr
Samples	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm X10 ⁴	ppm X10 ⁴	ppm
L21	11.00	18.60	87.30	447.70	107.10	3.30	7.00	0.90	0.16	3.50	2.07	1.03	241.30
L28	7.30	24.50	57.50	400.90	179.30	4.70	24.10	1.90	0.36	11.30	1.78	2.59	495.10
L29	6.70	19.50	80.90	797.80	130.30	3.40	6.10	0.50	0.19	3.80	3.56	1.33	327.10
L30	21.70	20.80	103.80	708.50	146.10	3.90	18.10	2.40	0.33	8.20	2.91	1.81	260.30
L37	8.20	23.50	48.00	436.40	262.60	5.70	14.70	1.30	0.50	10.30	1.40	3.37	488.80
Average:	10.98	21.38	75.50	558.26	165.08	4.20	14.00	1.40	0.31	7.42	2.34	2.03	362.52

Table 6: Concentrations of Some Selected Rare Earth Elements (REEs) in Fine-Grained Granite

Element	Th	Co	Rb	Ba	Zr	Hf	Nb	Ta	Ti	Ni	K	Ca	Sr
Sample	ppm	ppm	ppm x10 ²	ppm x10 ²	ppm x10 ²	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm X10 ⁴	ppm X10 ⁴	ppm x10 ²
L3	7.60	27.80	1.47	7.64	2.19	5.30	13.50	1.00	0.45	29.10	3.19	2.48	3.85
L6	8.80	18.20	0.85	1.29	2.05	5.90	10.80	1.10	0.25	13.30	2.47	1.50	5.41
L7	8.60	27.80	0.76	5.02	2.72	6.10	17.40	1.50	0.05	33.80	1.74	3.63	6.74
L9	1.90	25.80	1.17	7.43	1.57	4.00	11.40	0.50	0.25	20.70	2.81	2.62	4.08
L10	10.30	35.80	1.14	4.32	2.16	5.40	12.40	0.80	0.05	30.20	2.06	2.86	4.72
L13	10.70	30.80	0.91	1.32	1.35	3.50	11.20	1.40	0.36	25.30	2.71	2.68	6.01
L14	5.80	25.70	0.96	1.41	1.46	3.70	13.50	1.70	0.27	18.10	2.91	1.89	5.70
Average	7.67	27.41	1.03	9.21	1.93	4.84	12.89	1.14	0.24	24.36	2.56	2.52	5.22

Note: Th – Thorium, Co – Cobalt, Rb – Rubidium, Ba – Barium, Zr – Zirconium Hf – Hafnium, Nb – Niobium, Ta – Tantalum, Ti - Titanium, Ni - Nickel, K - Potassium, Ca - Calcium, Strontium.

Table 7: Concentrations of Some Selected Rare Earth Elements (REE) in Migmatite Gneiss

Element	Th	Co	Rb	Ba	Zr	Hf	Nb	Ta	Ti	Ni	K	Ca	Sr
Sample	Ppm	ppm	ppm x10 ²	ppm x10 ²	ppm x10 ²	Ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm X10 ⁴	ppm X10 ⁴	ppm x10 ²
L18	11.50	20.10	0.85	6.95	1.09	3.20	10.40	1.10	0.14	4.20	3.23	1.23	2.71
L25	14.80	18.40	0.88	5.64	0.63	1.80	3.70	0.40	0.12	2.50	3.74	0.70	1.25
L26	2.40	23.00	1.11	5.46	0.98	2.80	4.90	0.50	0.10	3.00	3.74	0.98	3.28
L27	14.20	34.10	1.48	4.68	2.08	23.90	39.50	3.30	0.92	46.60	2.57	2.08	2.08
L39	12.30	17.00	2.01	5.95	2.24	7.00	16.80	1.60	0.65	23.80	4.22	0.53	1.20
Average	11.04	22.52	1.26	5.73	1.40	7.74	15.06	1.38	0.39	16.02	3.50	1.10	2.11

Table 8. Concentrations of Some Selected Rare Earth Metals (REE) in Schist

REE	Th	Co	Rb	Ba	Zr	Hf	Nb	Ta	Ti	Ni	K	Ca	Sr
Sample	ppm	ppm	ppm x10 ²	ppm x10 ²	ppm x10 ²	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm	ppm X10 ⁴	ppm X10 ⁴	ppm x10 ²
L15	33.50	21.80	1.36	6.57	8.67	5.50	13.30	2.10	0.31	13.80	2.94	2.37	3.30
L16	12.90	18.30	1.24	6.28	1.92	5.10	14.50	1.30	0.28	6.90	2.62	1.52	1.53
L17	13.30	17.40	1.30	6.35	1.62	4.30	11.00	1.20	0.24	6.40	3.11	1.74	2.18
L38	12.40	22.10	1.40	6.90	1.55	4.30	11.60	2.20	0.29	16.50	2.96	2.37	3.35
Av	18.03	19.90	1.32	6.52	3.44	4.80	12.60	1.70	0.28	10.90	2.91	2.00	2.58

Note: Th – Thorium, Co – Cobalt, Rb – Rubidium, Ba – Barium, Zr – Zirconium Hf – Hafnium, Nb – Niobium, Ta – Tantalum, Ti - Titanium, Ni - Nickel, K - Potassium, Ca - Calcium, Sr – Strontium.

DISCUSSION

Mineralization

Concentrations of some selected trace elements including gold (Au) and Arsenic (As) in the various lithologic units established are presented (Tables 1 - 4), while the average concentration of gold and arsenic (its pathfinder) in the different lithologic units are graphically presented (Figure 2). The concentrations of some selected rare earth elements (REEs) for each unit are also presented (Tables 5-8) from which plots are made to determine the likely origin of the lithologic units.

Figure 2. Average concentration of gold and arsenic in all rock types (C.G. - Coarse-Grained Granite, F.G. - Fine-Grained Granite, and, M. Gneiss - Migmatite Gneiss)

Genesis of the granite

The $K_2O - SiO_2$ diagram after Keith (1983) revealed that the granites are predominantly Calc-Alkaline Series and marginally Alkali-Calcic Series (Figure 3). This conforms with Keith's proposal that major gold deposits are linked with calcic, calc-alkaline and alkaline series; while the alkali-calcic series give rise to major precious metal deposits. This was also supported by results from Leveille et al. (1988) that gold deposits are found more in the reduced rather than the oxidized intrusions across the full alkalinity range. The low values of K_2O , Al_2O_3 and Na_2O with relatively high values in MgO and CaO resembles the rock suites found around Burum-Takalafia near Abuja (Ako, 2006). Average values of K/Rb plot (Figure 4) the coarse and fine-grained gave values above 150. This is an indication of remobilized granite. Plots of oxides of aluminium, iron, magnesium, calcium, sodium and potassium (granites only) against that of silicon generally have a slope of less than 2.0 also confirmed that the granites are remobilized crustal materials. (Schroll, 1976).

Figure 3. K_2O/SiO_2 diagram for unaltered intrusive rocks related to gold deposits. After Keith (1983)

Genesis of the gneiss

Results of plot of K/Rb (> 150) (Figure 4) revealed that the gneiss is actually para-gneiss which was confirmed by the Co average values of $> 10\text{ppm}$ (Table 7). Plots of Ni/Co ratio (Figure 5) a value of < 1 also confirmed this that the gneiss a para-gneiss (Schroll, 1976).

Figure 4. K - Rb Plots

Figure 5. Ni - Co Plots

Genesis of the schist

The schist is para-schist going by the same reason with that of gneiss but in addition, it is also confirmed that the gneiss is a crustal material going by the Rb/Sr (> 0.25) (Figure 6) (Schroll, 1976).

Figure 6. Rb - Sr Plots

GEOCHEMICAL ASSAY OF GOLD MINERALIZATION

An anomaly of about 5.6 ppm was found within the schist and concentration and distribution fans out and diminishes away from this zone as illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Geochemical Map of the study area

CONCLUSIONS

Beni and its environs of Kafin-Koro, is situated within the basement complex of central Nigeria. The area is underlain by four different rock types comprising fine-grained granitic rocks, coarse-grained granitic rocks, banded gneiss and schist. Other less prominent rock types are the quartz and pegmatite veins. The coarse-grained granitic rocks are found in the southwestern portion of the studied area. Its occurrence extends from Kafin-Koro up to Kongo and Abolo. The fine-grained granitic rocks underlie the central and northern parts, while the northeast and eastern areas are underlain by the schist and banded gneiss respectively. Structurally, the general trend of the rocks is mainly NNE-SSW while they have a dip of 72° W. The rocks are highly faulted and in some cases disjointed. Petrological and geochemical data indicate mineralization of gold with an anomaly around Beni. This mineralization accompanied the intense shearing and mylonitization around the north-eastern area underlain by the schist. Economically, gold and some other rare earth elements and transitional metals can be won at a profit in the project area.

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